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Cyber Risk Analysis Using Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process for Cybersecurity Readiness in Small and Medium Enterprises in Thailand

Wilas Witheeprai¹, Prasan Wongkitisophon¹, Chanapatt Pattaramaetakul¹,
Prasong Praneetpolgrang^{1*}

¹Information Technology program, Graduate College of Management, Sripatum University, Thailand

Abstract

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in Thailand's economy. However, they face increasingly severe cyber threats daily due to budget constraints and a lack of cybersecurity expertise. So, effective cyber risk management is essential to allocate the limited resources to respond to cyber threats. This study aims to analyze and prioritize cyber risk factors in Thai SMEs using the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP), which better handles uncertainties in human subjective decision-making than the traditional AHP. This study categorizes cyber risks into five main categories: financial, governance, human, operational, and reputational. By collecting the cyber risks prioritized by 15 experts, the results of Fuzzy AHP analysis reveal that human, financial, and operational risks have the most significant impact on SMEs, accounting for over 70% of all five risks. The result can serve as an efficiency guideline for planning and allocating cybersecurity resources for SMEs to overcome the limitations.

Keywords: Cyber risk, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process, Cybersecurity, Small and medium enterprises

1. INTRODUCTION

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have a crucial role in the global economy, accounting for over 90% of all businesses and building more than 60% of global employment [1]. In Thailand, SMEs have contributed more than one-third of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and are the main source of employment [2].

To keep the competitive advantage, SMEs have been transformed into digital operations and depend on the driving of digital technologies such as cloud, e-commerce, and remote work. Consequently, by depending on many digital technologies, they face cyber threats that are increasingly frequent and severe. The 2024 Global Cybersecurity Outlook reported that cybersecurity incidents are ranked as high-level risks to businesses worldwide [3] and as the greatest risk to the operations of firms of all sizes [4]. Moreover, SMEs are the main targets of cybercriminals because of the lack of capabilities to protect themselves, which makes SMEs an easier target compared to large firms [5].

SMEs' cyber risks not only impact from a technical perspective but also various business operations. From the study of COSO's Risk Assessment in Practice [6] with ISO/IEC 27005:2018

[7]. This study identified cyber risks into five categories, including financial, governance, human, operational, and reputational risks.

Effective cyber risk management needs to prioritize the risks to allocate limited resources and budget efficiently to the most impactful risk [8]. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [9] is widely recognized as a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) in the cybersecurity risk assessment [10]. However, traditional AHP has limitations to uncertainty and vagueness from experts' subjective decision-making [11]. The integration of Zadeh's fuzzy set [12] with the AHP process represented Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP), which can accommodate the ambiguity of assessing. It provides better results that reflect the reality of human decision-making.

This study applies Buckley's Fuzzy AHP calculation [13] as a guideline to prioritize cyber risks of SMEs by collecting the opinion from 15 experts in five risk categories: financial, governance, human, operational, and reputational risks, which align with current cybersecurity assessment research [14],[15].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 SMEs' cybersecurity challenges

SMEs face increasingly complex and severe cybersecurity challenges. Study of [16] points out that SMEs have limitations of resources, budget, and expertise when compared to large firms, making them the primary target to be attacked by cybercriminals. In this line [17], a systematic literature review was conducted to identify four main challenges of SMEs, including a lack of awareness, unsustainable guidelines, limited cybersecurity knowledge, and constrained financial resources.

In the Thai context, [18] studied the evaluation methods and cyber risk reduction strategies for SMEs, indicating Thai SMEs still have a lack of resources and limited technological knowledge, fragmented governance, and a low rate of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) in cybersecurity [19]. In addition, the national cyber security agency (NCSA) reported that most of the cyberattack incidents occurred because of inefficiency in preventing systems and also a lack of proper cybersecurity measures [20].

2.2 Cyber risk classification

Cyber risks have an impact on multi-dimensional aspects, not only in the technical dimensions but also in coverage of various business operations. This study classified the cyber risks into five categories based on COSO [6] and ISO/IEC 27005:2018 [7], including financial, governance, human, operational, and reputational risks.

Financial risk indicates that a cyberattack will be a financial burden for SMEs, both direct and indirect. Direct costs such as costs of data recovery, legal fines, and investigation expenses. Meanwhile, indirect costs include loss of revenue due to business disruption, or loss of intellectual property, etc. [21].

Governance risk. The NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 elevates the Govern function as a key function to cyber risk management [22]. Cyber risk management involves a

responsibility structure, strategic decision-making, and determining risk appetite to align with business objectives to ensure that the firm can conduct the business operation without violating any laws or commercial contracts [23].

Human risk. Most of the causes of data breaches involve human factors such as clicking on phishing links, using weak passwords, and falling victim to social engineering. Cybercriminals usually use psychological techniques to bait the employees, for example, claiming authority and building trust [24], which indicates that advanced technology systems alone are not enough to protect human vulnerabilities. Therefore, continuing training and awareness-building are key strategies to reduce human risk [25].

Operational risk. Cyberattacks such as ransomware and distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) can cause operational disruptions. Not only losing data or paying ransom, but also losing operational controls, an irresponsible working machine, and the production process is stopped. Additionally, cyberattacks can expand to the supply chain and customers [26].

Reputational risk. Successful cyberattacks can have a severely negative impact on a firm’s reputation, because customers and stakeholders’ trust are intangible resources that influence a firm’s survival. Effective cyber risk management is the crucial factor for keeping a great firm’s reputation [27].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Fuzzy AHP calculations in this study follow the guidelines from Buckley (1985) [13], due to its uncomplex calculation method, and provide unique results. The procedure is as follows.

3.1 Cyber risks comparison

The identified risks, including financial, governance, human, operational, and reputational risks, had been assessed for pairwise comparison by 15 experts using the Saaty scale [9], as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Saaty’s scale for pairwise comparison.

Intensity of important	Definition
1	Equal importance
3	Moderate importance
5	Strong importance
7	Very strong importance
9	Extreme importance
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values

The pairwise comparison between risk factors. If i is stronger than j at level 5, the value in matrix a_{ij} will be 5; conversely, the value in matrix a_{ji} will be 1/5 or 0.2 by the reciprocal property. As shown in Equation 1.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \cdots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

3.2 Consistency ratio calculation

To examine whether the experts’ pairwise comparison is reasonable and consistent. If the consistency ratio (CR) ≤ 0.10 , it indicates that the pairwise comparison results are reliable; if CR > 0.10 , it represents the conflict in pairwise comparison. It’s necessary to perform a pairwise comparison again. The CR calculation procedure is as follows.

(1) Normalize the data in the matrix as shown in Equation 2.

$$\tilde{a}_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}} \tag{2}$$

Where

\tilde{a}_{ij} is the normalized value in row i and column j .

a_{ij} is the original comparison value from the experts, in row i and column j .

$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}$ is the sum of all values in column j .

(2) Priority vector calculation to determine the important weight of risk factors, by calculating the mean in each row from the normalized value. As shown in Equation 3.

$$w_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{ij} \tag{3}$$

Where

w_i is the priority vector of factor i .

n is the total number of factors being compared.

$\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{ij}$ is the sum of the normalized values in row i .

(3) Maximum eigenvalue calculation, by calculating the λ_{max} value. If the matrix is perfectly consistent, λ_{max} will be exactly equal to n . However, there is often a slight inconsistency. The calculation is shown in Equation 4.

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(Aw)_i}{w_i} \tag{4}$$

Where

λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue.

$(Aw)_i$ is the value obtained by multiplying the original comparison matrix (A) by the weight vector (w) and then extracting the value in row i .

(4) Consistency index (CI) calculation. To measure the level of deviation and error in experts' decision-making. If $CI = 0$, it means the assessments are perfectly consistent. The calculation is shown in Equation 5.

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \tag{5}$$

(5) Consistency ratio (CR) calculation to examine whether the inconsistency is within acceptable criteria, see Equation 6.

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{6}$$

Where

RI (Random Index) is a Saaty's standard constant, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Random Index.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
RI	0	0	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49	1.51	1.48	1.56	1.57	1.58

3.3 Fuzzy Operation

The pairwise comparison results of experts who have passed the CR assessment are converted into TFNs, where l stands for lower, m for middle, and u for upper. The method for converting to TFNs is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Conversion of crisp values to triangular fuzzy numbers.

Crisp Values	TFN (l, m, u)	Reciprocal TFN
1	(1,1,1)	(1,1,1)
2-8	($x-1, x, x+1$)	($1/(x+1), 1/x, 1/(x-1)$)
9	(8,9,9)	(1/9,1/9,1/8)

(1) Aggregating the TFNs of all 15 experts into a single representative value using the geometric mean for each component of the TFN preserves the accuracy of the reciprocal matrix, as shown in Equation 7.

$$\tilde{a}_{ij} = \left(\prod_{k=1}^K l_{ij}^k \right)^{1/K}, \left(\prod_{k=1}^K m_{ij}^k \right)^{1/K}, \left(\prod_{k=1}^K u_{ij}^k \right)^{1/K} \tag{7}$$

Where

\tilde{a}_{ij} is aggregated fuzzy number.

K is the total number of experts.

$l_{ij}^k, m_{ij}^k, u_{ij}^k$ is the triangular fuzzy number assigned by expert k to criterion i relative to criterion j .

(2) The calculation of the fuzzy geometric mean for each row is shown in Equation 8.

$$\tilde{r}_i = \left(\prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{ij} \right)^{1/n} \tag{8}$$

Where

\tilde{r}_i is fuzzy triangular geometric mean value.

n is the total number of risks.

(3) Calculation of fuzzy weights using normalization by $\frac{l}{\sum u}, \frac{m}{\sum m}, \frac{u}{\sum l}$ which yields the weights of each criterion in TFN form $(l_{w_i}, m_{w_i}, u_{w_i})$ as shown in Equation 9.

$$\tilde{w}_i = \tilde{r}_i \otimes \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{r}_i \right)^{-1} \tag{9}$$

Where

\tilde{w}_i is fuzzy weight of risk i

(4) Defuzzification converts the TFN value to a single value using the center-of-area method, yielding the average that represents the TFN, as shown in Equation 10.

$$DF_i = \frac{l_w + m_w + u_w}{3} \tag{10}$$

Where

DF_i is the defuzzified value of risk i .

(5) The final weight for each criterion was obtained by normalization, as shown in Equation 11.

$$w_i^{final} = \frac{DF_i}{\sum_{k=1}^n DF_k} \tag{11}$$

Where

w_i^{final} is final weight of risk i .

$\sum_{k=1}^n DF_k$ is the sum of the DF values across all criteria.

4. RESULTS

The results of the pairwise comparison by the 15 experts passed the CR check, with values ranging from 0.0567 to 0.0947, indicating consistency in the experts’ evaluations. Once the crisp values were converted to TFNs, the aggregated evaluation results from all the experts were obtained as lower, middle, and upper values. These three values were then combined into a single value using the fuzzy geometric mean, and the fuzzy weights were calculated, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Fuzzy weights of each risk.

Risk	Lower	Middle	Upper
Financial	0.1469	0.2253	0.3460
Governance	0.1033	0.1554	0.2435
Human	0.1584	0.2561	0.3976
Operational	0.1459	0.2249	0.3428
Reputational	0.0916	0.1383	0.2178

After obtaining the fuzzy weights for each risk, defuzzification and normalization were performed to derive risk-ranking values, as shown in Table 5. The ranking results indicate that human risk has the highest risk (25.43%), followed by financial and operational risk with similar values at 22.49% and 22.34%, respectively, then governance risk (15.72%), and reputation risk (14.02%).

Table 5. Cyber risk prioritization.

Rank	Risk	DF	Weight
1	Human	0.2707	0.2543
2	Financial	0.2394	0.2249
3	Operational	0.2379	0.2234
4	Governance	0.1674	0.1572
5	Reputational	0.1492	0.1402

5. DISSUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study prioritizes the cyber risks of Thai SMEs. The results show that human risk is the most crucial factor in Thai SMEs context, follow by financial and operational risks. These three aspects influence over 70%. Another 30% were taken by governance and reputational risks.

Human risk is ranked as the first priority, consistent with Verizon's 2024 data breach investigations report, which states that humans are the key factor involved in 68% of all data breaches [28]. Despite advances in security technologies, somehow human error remains the main cause of vulnerability for attackers to exploit by using cognitive biases and users' behavioral patterns [29].

Financial and operational risks are ranked second and third, with a significant similar weight. IBM's 2025 cost of a data breach states that the average cost of a data breach worldwide reached 4.4 million USD [30]. The impact of cyberattacks can disrupt business operations, resulting in significant revenue losses for SMEs, which can be far more severe than for larger corporations due to budgetary constraints and limited capital reserves. It has been reported that around 75% of SMEs attacked by ransomware are at risk of having to shut down [31].

Governance risk is ranked fourth. This might be interpreted as governance risk is less important than financial and operational risks in experts' opinion. Reflect that Thai SMEs have still have a limited level of awareness of cyber risk governance issues, with fragmented governance [18] which can lead to unsystematic decision-making and inefficient resource allocation.

Governance risk is ranked fourth. This might be interpreted as governance risk is less important than financial and operational risks in the experts' opinion. Reflect that Thai SMEs still have a limited level of awareness of cyber risk governance issues, with fragmented governance [18], which can lead to unsystematic decision-making and inefficient resource allocation.

Lastly, reputational risk, SMEs have a smaller customer base and public awareness than large firms, which might affect the experts' opinion to decide that reputational risk is less of a concern than the other risks. However, customer and stakeholder trust is an intangible asset [27]. Negative reputational damage can lead to loss of customers and long-term business opportunities.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study ranks the cyber risks of Thai SMEs based on assessments by 15 experts, providing academic and practical value to SMEs by highlighting the importance of preparing for cybersecurity. However, this research certainly has limitations. Firstly, the limited number of experts may not fully reflect the diversity of Thai SMEs. Secondly, the research categorizes risks into five main categories, which may not cover sub-issues or specific topics.

Future research should therefore increase the number of experts to cover a wider range of dimensions and may consider cyber risk from other perspectives, as well as use the other MCDM techniques such as Fuzzy TOPSIS, Fuzzy ANP, or Intuitionistic Fuzzy AHP.

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